

Toward Stable Electrode/Electrolyte Interface of P2-Layered Oxide for Rechargeable Na-Ion Batteries

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ABSTRACT:

The electrochemical properties of P2-Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂ layered oxide, which is a promising cathode material for rechargeable Na-ion batteries (NIBs), are evaluated with an optimized in-house ionic liquid (IL)-based electrolyte, and its performance is compared with that using carbonate-based electrolyte. The IL-based system reveals better electrochemical performance at room temperature than the carbonate electrolyte-based one at 0.1C and 1C, especially in terms of cycling stability, with a 97% capacity retention after 100 deep cycles (0.1C). The electrode/ electrolyte interface is thoroughly studied in both systems by means of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy so as proof that the formed interface is crucial to optimizing the electrochemical performance of NIBs. The carbonate-based system shows a thin, inhomogeneous, and unstable interface layer, while the IL-based one exhibits an even thinner but homogeneous and more stable interface, which may result in safer and longer-lasting NIBs.

KEYWORDS: Na-layered oxide, solid permeable interface, carbonate-based electrolyte, ionic liquid electrolyte, Na-ion batteries

1. INTRODUCTION

Li-ion batteries (LIBs) are the best energy storage devices for portable electronics and electric vehicles. However, several concerns have arisen regarding the Li availability and price instability as well as concerns regarding the Co resources, especially considering that Co is the key element in the present cathodes for LIBs.^{1,2} Concurrently, Na-ion batteries (NIBs) are considered as the upcoming energy storage technology for large-scale stationary applications and light electromobility owing to the promise of substantial cost reductions. In fact, Na is almost inexhaustible and evenly distributed in the Earth's crust, thus making it easily accessible and cheaper than Li.¹⁻³ However, the electrochemical performance of NIBs has still to be improved for this technology to reach the commercial stage. The competitiveness of NIBs can be improved, on the one hand, through electrode material optimization and, on the other hand, finding a suitable electrode/electrolyte configuration that allows the formation of a good protective layer hindering the electrode and electrolyte degradation upon cycling.

45 Among the high-energy layered oxide cathode materials for NIBs, those with the general
46 formula Na_xTMO_2 (TM = one or more transition metal/s, such as, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Ti, Cu)
47 are the most promising candidates due to their high specific capacity and relatively facile
48 synthesis.^{4,5} Mn-rich layered oxides are particularly interesting owing to their typically
49 high reversible capacity. Besides, Mn is abundant in the Earth's crust, environmentally
50 friendly, and has low cost.⁵ However, Mn-layered oxides have some drawbacks such as
51 the presence of Jahn–Teller-active MnIII ((t2g)3(eg)1), which causes poor capacity
52 retention due to structural strains,⁶ and Mn dissolution in carbonate-based
53 electrolytes.⁷ Nevertheless, the latter problem can be solved either by protecting the
54 electrode active material surface^{8,9} or by selecting alternative electrolytes that suppress
55 Mn dissolution.¹⁰

56
57 In order to improve the structural stability of Mn-based layered oxides, Yabuuchi et al.
58 substituted Mn by Fe, obtaining P2- $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{1/2}\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{O}_2$, which delivers a reversible
59 capacity of 190 mAh g^{-1} at 0.1C in carbonate-based electrolyte (1 M NaClO_4 in PC)
60 although 15% of the capacity fades after 30 cycles.¹¹ Recently, small amounts of
61 electrochemically active or inactive metals such as, Cu, Ti, Ni, and Mg have been
62 substituted into the Mn/Fe-layered oxides to mitigate their capacity fading. In terms of
63 capacity retention, these binary, ternary, or even quaternary layered oxides show
64 improvements in comparison to P2- $\text{Na}_x\text{Mn}_{1-y}\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_2$ ($0 \leq y \leq 1$) due to the substitutive
65 species providing structural stability, reduce the volume change upon cycling, increase
66 Na interlayer distance, and/or accommodate the electrochemically induced strain of
67 Mn^{III} .^{12–19}

68
69 Despite displaying several disadvantages such as low thermal stability, high volatility,
70 and flammability, carbonate-based electrolytes are still often chosen due to peculiar
71 features such as high ionic conductivity and low viscosity and density. In the past few
72 years, electrolytes based on some families of ionic liquids (ILs) have also attracted great
73 attention. Several studies can be found describing improvements on the electrochemical
74 properties of layered oxides in the presence of IL-based electrolytes although ILs have
75 lower ionic conductivity and higher viscosity and density.^{10,20–22} However, the
76 advantages of ILs are very attractive since ILs have a wider electrochemical stability
77 window, higher thermal stability, and negligible volatility and flammability compared to
78 carbonate-based electrolytes.²³ These result in safer and more environmentally friendly
79 NIBs, which are important priorities for stationary applications besides long lifetime and
80 low cost. An open issue with ILs is the cost: arguably, IL-based electrolytes are certainly
81 more expensive than carbonates, but they are fully recyclable, and then they can be
82 reused over and over.²⁴ Besides, the maintenance expenses and installation investments
83 can be reduced and outweigh the production cost.

84
85 The mitigation of Mn dissolution cannot be the only reason for the superior
86 electrochemical performance of IL-based systems. Indeed, the formation of suitable
87 electrode/electrolyte interfaces, namely, the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI)²⁵ also
88 known as a solid permeable interphase (SPI) for the positive electrode side²⁶ is the key.
89 The formation of an SEI/ SPI layer is expected since the typical operating voltage of the
90 cell is outside the electrolyte stability window (ESW). However, the formation of a
91 homogeneous and stable passivation layer is needed to widen the operating voltage of

92 the system while avoiding further electron transfer between the electrode and
93 electrolyte and the continuous electrolyte reduction/oxidation. The passivation layer
94 usually is formed during the initial electrochemical cycles. This layer formation is usually
95 more pronounced in the negative electrode than in the positive one although the layer
96 in both electrodes shows similar compositions.²⁷ Therefore, the study of the electrode/
97 electrolyte interface in the presence of carbonate- and IL-based electrolytes is of
98 paramount importance. In particular, unraveling the decomposition reactions in both
99 electrolytes is essential to understanding the differences in the electrochemical
100 performance and to developing NIBs with higher energy density and extended lifetime.
101 However, the electrode/ electrolyte interface investigations reported so far mostly have
102 focused on the SEI layer of negative electrodes such as hard carbons (HCs),²⁸ Na₂Ti₃O₇,²⁹
103 Sn,³⁰ Sb,³¹ SnSb/C,³² Cu₂Sb,³³ NaTi₂(PO₄)₃,³⁴ and NaTiOPO₄,³⁵ while only a few works can
104 be found on the positive electrodes.^{36,37} Furthermore, such interfaces have been
105 explored with carbonate-based electrolytes, and to the best of our knowledge, to date,
106 the comparison of an electrode/electrolyte interface on NIBs, formed with both
107 carbonate- and IL-based electrolytes, has only been performed for negative
108 electrodes.³⁸

109
110 In this work, the electrochemical response and the SPI characterization of P2-
111 Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂ (from here on referred to as NMFTO) layered oxide are reported.
112 NMFTO has been reported to deliver 140 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.1C and room temperature (R.T.),
113 with a capacity retention of 95% after 50 cycles using 1 M NaPF₆ EC:PC:FEC carbonate-
114 based electrolyte.¹³ Upon testing with the IL-based electrolyte (NaFSI:P111i4FSI) at 0.5C
115 and 50 °C, the material exhibited only 70 mAh g⁻¹ after 50 cycles (92% of the capacity
116 retention).²¹ Herein, the electrochemical properties of NMFTO are investigated with the
117 IL-based electrolyte (1:9 mol NaFSI in Pyr₁₄FSI, which corresponds to 0.35 M NaFSI) and
118 the carbonate-based electrolyte with FEC as the additive (1 M NaPF₆ in EC:PC with 2 wt
119 % FEC) upon 0.1C or 1C C-rates and 20 °C, rendering the comparison between both
120 electrolytes possible. Additionally, the SPI layer stability and composition have been
121 studied by means of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), while the morphology has
122 been evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in a half-cell configuration. The
123 nature of the SPI layer is correlated with the electrochemical performance of the NMFTO
124 layered oxide. It should be mentioned that recent reports³⁹ suggested that the presence
125 of metallic Na might influence the electrochemical and electrode/electrolyte interface
126 properties; however, it is essential to understand first the SEI/SPI evolution in half-cell
127 systems before moving to a more complex full-cell configuration.

128 129 2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

130 2.1. Synthesis of P2-Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂. NMFTO was synthesized by a solid-state
131 method, mixing stoichiometric amounts of anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (100%, Scharlab), Mn₂O₃
132 (98%, Alfa Aesar), Fe₂O₃ (97%, Alfa Aesar), and TiO₂ (100%, Sigma Aldrich). The resultant
133 powder was pelletized and annealed at 1000 °C for 6 h under ambient air and
134 transferred to a glovebox during cooling in order to avoid contact with the atmosphere.

135
136 2.2. Electrolyte Preparation. The carbonate-based electrolyte was prepared using 1 M
137 NaPF₆ (sodium hexafluorophosphate, battery grade, FluoroChem) in a mixture of EC
138 (ethylene carbonate, battery grade, UBE) and PC (propylene carbonate, battery grade,

139 UBE), with a weight ratio of 1:1. FEC (fluoroethylene carbonate; 2 wt %, DBASF) was
140 added to the electrolyte. For preparation of the IL-based electrolyte, commercially
141 available sodium salt NaFSI (sodium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide, 99.7%, Solvionic) was
142 mixed with an inhouse synthesized IL, namely, Pyr₁₄FSI (N-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium
143 bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide) in a 1:9 ratio, corresponding to 0.35 M concentration. The
144 synthesis of the IL has been previously reported in refs 40 and 41. The salt and IL were
145 pre-dried at 90 °C in a chamber connected to an oil vacuum pump ($\sim 10^{-3}$ mbar) overnight
146 and further intensively dried at 90 °C ([FSI]-based ILs) using a turbomolecular vacuum
147 pump ($\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar). The prepared electrolyte was mixed at R.T. via magnetic stirring
148 and dried at 50 °C under vacuum (with a turbomolecular vacuum pump, $\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar) in
149 a dry room (dew point of less than -70 °C).

150

151 2.3. Electrochemical Characterization. The electrodes were prepared by mixing 80%
152 active material with 10% carbon Super C65 (Timcal) and 10% poly(vinylidene fluoride)
153 (PVdF 6020 Solef, Arkema Group) in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, Sigma Aldrich). The
154 slurry was cast on battery-grade Al-foil and dried under dynamic vacuum at 120 °C. Disk
155 electrodes (12 mm diameter) were punched and pressed at 4 tons before assembling
156 half-cells in an Ar-filled glovebox (MBraun, H₂O and O₂ < 1 ppm). The performance was
157 tested using metallic Na disks (Acros Organics, 99.8%) as counter and reference
158 electrodes in Swagelok-type cells, a glass fiber (Whatman GF/A or GF/D) as the
159 separator, and 1 M NaPF₆ in EC:PC + 2 wt % FEC or 1:9 mol NaFSI in Pyr₁₄FSI as the
160 electrolyte. The galvanostatic measurements were carried out at 20 ± 2 °C in a Maccor
161 Series 4000 battery tester (USA) in the voltage window of 2.0–4.0 V vs Na/Na⁺ at 0.1C
162 and 1C rates.

163

164 2.4. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy. XPS experiments were performed on pristine
165 and OCV (open circuit voltage) electrodes and upon electrochemical cycling at different
166 (dis)charge states: 1st charge (4.0 V vs Na/Na⁺), 1st discharge (2.0 V vs Na/Na⁺), 10th
167 charge (4.0 V vs Na/Na⁺), and 10th discharge (2.0 V vs Na/Na⁺) at 0.1C. Note that a glass
168 fiber was used as the separator, and although some fiber might remain attached to the
169 electrode surface, in our case, the surface electrodes were free of fiber (see Figure S1).
170 The electrodes were rinsed with DMC before transferring to the XPS vacuum chamber
171 via an Ar-filled transfer holder (the samples were never exposed to air). A non-
172 monochromatic Mg K α ($h\nu = 1253.6$ eV) Xray source and a Phoibos 150 XPS
173 spectrometer equipped with a microchannel plate and a delay line detector (DLD) were
174 used. The scans were acquired with an X-ray source power of 100 W, 20 eV pass energy
175 (fixed analyzer transmission mode), and 0.1 eV energy step. The photoelectron spectra
176 were calibrated using the graphitic peak (sp² –C–C–) at 284.4 eV as reference. The
177 deconvolutions of the spectra were carried out with CasaXPS software using a nonlinear
178 Shirley-type background and a 70% Gaussian and 30% Lorentzian profile function.

179

180 2.5. Morphological Characterization. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of electrodes
181 at OCV and after cycling (10th charge) was performed on a Zeiss Crossbeam 340 field
182 emission electron microscope equipped with a Capella focused ion beam (FIB, gallium
183 ion source). All samples recovered from the cells were transferred to the microscope
184 under an Ar atmosphere using an airtight transfer box (Sample Transfer Shuttle,
185 SEMILAB). Micrographs were acquired from the top at a tilt angle of 54°. In the cross-

186 sectional configuration (after FIB preparation), the smartSEM software was used to
187 compensate for the image distortion due to the tilt of 54° to the optical axis. Since the
188 study focused on the deposits associated with SPI layer formation and electrolyte
189 decomposition, for FIB preparation, platinum sputtering was not performed to avoid the
190 introduction of an artificial coating layer. Therefore, to avoid curtaining and sample
191 damage, low currents of 1.5 nA and 300 pA at an acceleration voltage of 30 kV were
192 chosen to mill and polish the cross sections (see Figure S2 – SEM images before and after
193 FIB in an IL-based electrode).
194

195 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

196 3.1. Electrochemical Properties of P2-Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂. NMFTO crystallizes in a
197 hexagonal system (space group, *P6₃/mmc*) with the ABBA stacking sequence while the
198 Na atoms occupy the prismatic sites. The structural and morphological characterization
199 of NMFTO has already been performed, and more details can be found in our previous
200 works.¹³ Regarding the electrochemical properties, Figure 1 shows the 1st, 2nd, 50th,
201 and 100th charge/discharge profiles at a 0.1C rate in carbonate- (Figure 1a) and IL-based
202 (Figure 1b) electrolytes. Additionally, the capacity evolution upon electrochemical
203 cycling for the two electrolytes is also given (Figure 1c). Both cells show a smooth
204 galvanostatic profile with a small plateau close to 2.1 V versus Na/Na⁺ during the
205 discharge process, as previously reported.¹³ The only redox-active metal is MnIII/MnIV,
206 while FeIII and TiIV are electrochemically inactive in the studied voltage range (FeIII
207 inactivity has been previously confirmed by Mossbauer spectroscopy).¹³ The carbonate-
208 based system delivers a 2nd cycle discharge capacity of 156 mAh g⁻¹ and 147 mAh g⁻¹ at
209 the 50th cycle. These capacity values are higher than those obtained when using IL-
210 based electrolytes where, however, 138 and 137 mAh g⁻¹ are reached at the 2nd and
211 50th cycle, respectively. The inferior discharge capacities when IL is used as electrolyte
212 can be attributed to the higher viscosity and lower ionic conductivity of ILs compared
213 with the carbonate based electrolyte at 20 °C.⁴²⁻⁴⁵ Moreover, the lower capacity values
214 have been also related to the large charge-transfer resistance between metallic Na and
215 ILs.⁴⁶ Even so, after 100 cycles, the carbonate-based cell delivers 142 mAh g⁻¹ as
216 discharge capacity, while the IL-based one delivers 134 mAh g⁻¹. Therefore, the capacity
217 decays by almost 10% within 100 cycles in the carbonate-based cell, while in the IL-based
218 one, the capacity only fades by 3%, showing excellent electrochemical cycling stability
219 for the IL-based electrolyte.
220

221 The observed electrochemical response can be correlated with the different properties
222 of the formed SPI layer since in the studied voltage range (4.0–2.0 V vs Na/Na⁺), the
223 phase transitions that can affect the layered oxide performance are avoided and hence
224 are not the origin of the capacity fading in this study.^{47,48} Furthermore, the IL-based cell
225 presents lower 1st cycle irreversible capacity than the carbonate-based one (58 vs 69
226 mAh g⁻¹) and Coulombic efficiency (CE) values close to 100% from the 2nd cycle onward,
227 in contrast to the carbonate based system that needs a few more cycles to reach the
228 highest CE values. These results suggest that the IL-based electrolyte is more stable and
229 quickly forms a good SPI layer that protects the electrode against further reactions with
230 the electrolyte, showing higher stability upon electrochemical cycling, as it will be
231 thoroughly discussed in the next section in light of the XPS and SEM results.

233 Figure 1. P2-Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂ charge/discharge profile of the 1st, 2nd, 50th, and 100th cycle tested
 234 in (a) carbonate-based electrolyte (1 M NaPF₆ in EC:PC with 2 wt % FEC) and (b) IL-based electrolyte (1:9
 235 mol NaFSI in Pyr₁₄FSI). (c) Capacity (square and circle) and Coulombic efficiency (triangle) vs cycle number
 236 in carbonate (black) and IL (red) electrolytes at a 0.1C cycling rate within the voltage range of 4.0–2.0 V vs
 237 Na/Na⁺ at 20 ± 2 °C.

238

239 To evaluate the long-term cycling behavior, the NMFTO has been tested in both
 240 electrolytes at 1C for over 300 cycles (see Figure 2). The carbonate-based cell (Figure 2a)
 241 delivers 98 mAh g⁻¹ after 300 cycles, corresponding to 97% capacity retention with
 242 respect to the 2nd cycle discharge capacity. The higher capacity retention observed at a
 243 1C rate compared to a 0.1C rate indicates that the capacity fade is correlated with the
 244 reaction between the electrode and electrolyte, as previously suggested. Meanwhile,
 245 the IL-based cell delivers similar capacity, 102 mAh g⁻¹ after 300 cycles (Figure 2b). The
 246 capacity increase in the first 50 cycles of the IL-cell might be due to the high viscosity
 247 and low wettability of the electrode surface with the IL-based electrolyte. Besides, the
 248 similar delivered capacity at 1C in IL-based electrolyte is not expected since at 0.1C, the
 249 IL-based cell shows lower capacity values than the carbonate-based cell. This might be
 250 related to the electrode/electrolyte interface formed not only in NMFTO but also on the
 251 metallic Na. Indeed, at C/10, Na ions have more time to diffuse through the SPI layer,

252 being the limiting factor of the ionic conductivity; hence, the IL-based system shows
 253 lower capacity. Meanwhile, at 1C, the active surface area is the limiting factor.
 254 Considering the morphology and roughness of the SPI layer in carbonate-based systems,
 255 it is more than plausible that they deliver lower capacity values if compared with the IL-
 256 based system. Even so, contrary to previous investigations,²¹ the used IL electrolyte, 1:9
 257 mol NaFSI in Pyr₁₄FSI, allows obtaining good capacity values even at 1C and 20 °C.
 258

259 Figure 2. P2-Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂ charge/discharge profile of the 1st, 2nd, 50th, 100th, 200th, and 300th
 260 cycle tested in (a) carbonate based electrolyte (1 M NaPF₆ in EC:PC with 2 wt %) FEC and (b) IL-based
 261 electrolyte (1:9 mol NaFSI in Pyr₁₄FSI). (c) Capacity (square and circle) and Coulombic efficiency (triangle)
 262 vs cycle number in carbonate (black) and IL (red) electrolytes at a 1C rate within the voltage range of
 263 4.0–2.0 V vs Na/Na⁺ at 20 ± 2 °C.

264 Summarizing, it can be stated that the IL-based electrolyte provides more stable
 265 electrochemical cycling at low and high current densities in comparison to the
 266 carbonate-based cell at 20 °C, thus making it very attractive for practical application in
 267 NIBs.

268 3.2. Electrode/Electrolyte Interface Study of P2-Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂. The XPS spectra
 269 of the electrodes cycled in both electrolytes were collected by using Mg Kα (hν = 1253.6
 270 eV) as the photon source, which results in roughly 10 nm probing depth. Additionally,

271 high-resolution scans were acquired with low X-ray intensity in order to avoid the
272 formation of new surface species induced by exposure to X rays whose occurrence has
273 been previously demonstrated.²⁹ Regarding the stability of IL electrolytes, Figure S3
274 shows the evolution of the F 1s spectrum before and after 3 h of X-ray exposure. Fluorine
275 being one of the most sensitive elements owing to the intrinsically reactive nature to X-
276 rays of F containing polymeric species present in the electrode PVdF and considering
277 that no differences can be found in both F 1s peaks, it can be concluded that the surface
278 species observed are not induced by exposure to X-rays.

279

280 3.2.1. Evolution of SPI Layer in Carbonate-Based Electrolyte System. The
281 evolution of the SPI layer upon electrochemical cycling can be inferred from Figure 3
282 where the C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s core-level spectra of NMFTO electrodes as made (pristine)
283 and assembled in cells (both at OCV and cycled) with the carbonate-based electrolyte
284 are presented. More details about the peak assignment and binding energy are found in
285 Table S1. The XPS spectra of the pristine electrode, bottom panels of Figure 3, are
286 dominated by the contribution from the electrode components. The C 1s photoelectron
287 spectrum exhibits a main peak at 284.4 eV (–C–C– bond) corresponding to C65⁴⁹ along
288 with contributions at 286.4 and 290.9 eV, which can be assigned to the –CH₂ and –CF₂
289 groups from PVdF.⁵⁰ The latter group is also observed in the F 1s spectrum at ~688.3 eV.
290 The O 1s spectrum shows a small peak close to 530 eV corresponding to NMFTO.³⁶ The
291 outermost surface of the pristine electrode shows carbonaceous/oxygenated species
292 observed in C 1s and O 1s core-level spectra (more details in Table S1) such as
293 hydrocarbons (–CH), species with carbonyl groups (–CO_x–), and carbons bound to two
294 oxygens, such as alkyl carbonates (–CO₂–), and three oxygens, like sodium carbonate
295 (–CO₃).^{29,49} These species are typically detected on top of the layered oxides due to their
296 high reactivity toward moisture.^{29,36,51,52} Additionally, the F 1s spectrum shows a very
297 small peak at 685 eV corresponding to NaF, around 2% in relation to the –CF₂ signal.
298 Considering that the only source of fluorine can be PVdF, its dehydrofluorination
299 reaction must occur during electrode preparation. This reaction takes place because the
300 alkalinity of the slurry increases due to the formed NaRCO₃ (R = alkyl chain), Na₂CO₃
301 dissolved into NMP,⁵³ and the generation of NaOH from adsorbed water. From all the
302 above, it can be concluded that a very thin layer exists on the electrode surface before
303 any electrochemical activity takes place, this layer being mainly formed during the
304 layered oxide synthesis and electrode preparation.

305

306 Figure 3. C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s core-level spectra for the P2- $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$ pristine electrode and at
 307 OCV and different charge states during electrochemical cycling tested in carbonate-based electrolyte (1
 308 M NaPF_6 in EC:PC, 2 wt % FEC).

309

310 The electrode surface after exposure to the electrolyte has been studied, assembling a
 311 cell and keeping it for 12 h in open circuit conditions (i.e., OCV). The areas of the two
 312 main peaks of the pristine electrode, C65 in the C 1s and $-\text{CF}_2$ in the F 1s, are slightly
 313 reduced while the intensity of the peaks corresponding to carbonaceous/oxygenated
 314 species ($-\text{CO}$, $-\text{C}=\text{O}$, $-\text{CO}_2$, and $-\text{CO}_3$) and NaF increases. This suggests that EC and PC
 315 solvents are already decomposed just being in contact with the active material and
 316 metallic Na. On the one hand, the layered oxides can act as a reducing agent,⁵³ and on
 317 the other hand, the high reactivity of metallic Na promotes the reduction of the
 318 solvents.^{39,54} The formed species are soluble in the electrolyte and may diffuse to the
 319 cathode surface.^{55,56} Moreover, at OCV, the increased formation of NaF may have
 320 several origins, namely, the PVdF dehydrofluorination, NaPF_6 salt decomposition (NaPF_6
 321 $\rightarrow \text{NaF} + \text{PF}_5$),⁵⁷ and/or FEC decomposition resulting from the contact with the metallic
 322 Na electrode^{58,59} and/or the reducing behavior of the NMFTO positive electrode.⁵³

323

324 As observed in both C 1s and O 1s spectra, after the 1st electrochemical charge to 4.0 V
 325 vs Na/Na^+ , more $-\text{COC}-$ and $-\text{CO}_3$ species are formed due to further decomposition
 326 reactions of carbonate solvents. Additionally, the NaPF_6 salt is decomposed to
 327 fluorophosphates (NaPF_xO_y), as can be seen from the peak at 687 eV of the F 1s
 328 spectrum.³⁶

329

330 After the 1st discharge, a thicker SPI layer is formed, as can be inferred from the
 331 significant intensity decrease observed for the $-\text{C}-\text{C}-$ and $-\text{CF}_2$ peaks, which are ascribed
 332 to electrode components, C65 and PVdF, respectively. The main compounds observed
 333 in the SPI layer after one cycle (1st discharge state) are PEO (poly(ethylene oxide)),
 334 NaRCO_3 , Na_2CO_3 , NaPF_xO_y , and NaF from solvents and additive reduction, salt
 335 decomposition, and/or PVdF dehydrofluorination.

336

337 In order to study the stability of the electrode/electrolyte interface upon repeated
 338 electrochemical sodiation/desodiation, the SPI layer on the NMFTO electrodes was
 339 investigated after 10 cycles both at the charged and discharged states. As shown in

340 Figure 3, there is an indication that the SPI is continuously growing, thus forming a
 341 thicker layer after 10 cycles (C65 signal disappeared). The thickness of the SPI layer can
 342 be estimated from the photoelectron escape length. Considering the inelastic mean free
 343 path (IMFP), as described by Tanuma et al.,⁶⁰ and the photon energy used, 95% of the
 344 C65 photoelectrons detected by XPS originate from within 7 nm deep from the electrode
 345 surface. The C65 signal vanishes after 10 cycles, thus suggesting that the SPI layer
 346 formed on the electrode surface is thicker than 7 nm. The composition of the SPI layer
 347 after 10 cycles is similar to that observed in the 1st cycle, with Na₂CO₃ and NaF being the
 348 main surface species, which are characteristic of the SPI layer formed in the presence
 349 of carbonate-based electrolytes with an FEC additive. To fully identify the outermost SPI
 350 layer composition, the Na Auger parameter (α) was calculated. It was previously
 351 demonstrated²⁹ that the Auger parameter is a powerful approach to identify the Na-
 352 based electrode/electrolyte interface species when the peak assignment is complicated
 353 due to the overlapping of several components of the photoelectron peaks and partial
 354 surface charging effects. The Auger parameter is calculated by considering the binding
 355 energy of the Na 1s photoelectron and the kinetic energy of the Na KL₂₃L₂₃ Auger
 356 peaks.⁶¹ The fits of both peaks are shown in Figure S4, so the peak position can be
 357 determined. The obtained Auger parameter (α) values and the corresponding peak
 358 assignment are summarized in Table 1.

359
 360
 361

Table 1. Auger Parameter for Na-Based Species of the SPI Layer Formed in a Carbonate-Based Electrolyte at Different Charge States

Charge state	Auger parameter (eV)	Species
Pristine	2061.7	NMFTO ^a + Na ₂ CO ₃
OCV	2061.0	Na ₂ CO ₃
1 st charge	2062.2	Na-F species, e.g., NaPF _x O _y ^a
1 st discharge	2060.6	Na ₂ CO ₃ + NaRCO ₃ ^a
10 th charge	2059.7	NaF
10 th discharge	2060.5	Na ₂ CO ₃ + NaRCO ₃

362

^a Estimated from ref. 62 and 63

363 The Na-based Auger parameter is surface-sensitive because of the high binding energy
 364 of the Na 1s photoelectron that, in turn, has low kinetic energy and a short IMFP. This
 365 means that the pristine NMFTO electrode is slightly covered by Na₂CO₃, which is in
 366 agreement with the C 1s and O 1s photoelectron spectra. In the OCV condition, more
 367 Na₂CO₃ is coating the electrode's surface due to the mentioned reduction of organic
 368 solvents. However, after cycling, the electrode's outermost surface is covered by
 369 fluorinated species in the charged state and by more carbonaceous species in the
 370 discharged state. The observed behavior is corroborated by the photoelectron spectra
 371 analysis (see Figure 3) and is in agreement with the reported results for other Na-based
 372 electrodes.^{29,36}

373

374 To summarize, analysis of the XPS data by means of photoelectron peak deconvolution
 375 and determination of the Auger parameter provides the SPI layer composition and its
 376 evolution upon electrochemical cycling. The SPI is formed by fluorinated species
 377 (NaPF_xO_y and NaF) that at the discharged state are covered by carbonaceous species
 378 such as, PEO, Na₂CO₃, and NaRCO₃. The latter species are highly soluble in the electrolyte

379 and dissolve during the desodiation, thus not providing a stable SPI layer. As a result,
380 the NMFTO electrodes show lower cycling stability than in IL-based electrolyte.

381

382

383 3.2.2. Evolution of SPI Layer in IL-Based Electrolyte System. The SPI layer formed
384 on the surface of NMFTO electrodes cycled in the IL-based electrolyte was also studied
385 under the same experimental conditions used for the carbonate-based electrolyte.
386 Figure 4 shows the C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s core-level spectra of electrodes cycled in the IL-
387 based electrolyte, while Table S2 summarizes the binding energy of each observed
388 species. Comparing the C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s photoelectron spectra evolution upon
389 electrochemical cycling of both systems, obvious differences can be observed. First, the
390 spectra of all electrodes at various states of charge are dominated by the signals of C65
391 at 284.4 eV (C 1s) and PVdF (-CF₂) at ~688.3 eV (F 1s) electrode components. Second,
392 the peak assigned to the NMFTO active material at ~530 eV (O 1s) is still observed after
393 10 cycles although the intensity/ area of C65 and NMFTO is slightly reduced after
394 electrochemical cycling.^{49,50} Third, the overall shape of the C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s core-level
395 spectra changes to a much lower extent than those recorded for the electrodes in the
396 carbonate-based electrolyte. These results suggest that the SPI layer forms also in the
397 IL-based electrolyte, but it is thinner (below 7 nm considering Tanuma's model
398 aforementioned)⁶⁰ than that forming in the carbonate-based electrolyte. This is in
399 agreement with the earlier reported excellent cycling stability of the IL-based cell over
400 100 cycles at C/10 and 1C.

400

401 Figure 4. C 1s, F 1s, and O 1s core-level spectra for the P2- Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.1}Ti_{0.1}O₂ cathode electrode at
402 different charge states during electrochemical cycling tested in IL-based electrolyte (1:9 mol NaFSI in
403 Pyr₁₄FSI).

404

405 Regarding the composition of the IL-SPI layer, although some hydrocarbon (-CH-), alkyl
406 carbonates (-CO₂-), and sodium carbonate (-CO₃) can be found in the pristine
407 electrode, after cycling, there is no evidence of further formation (the area of the
408 corresponding species is similar upon the electrochemical cycling) due to the fact that
409 IL-based electrolyte decomposition reactions do not form these kinds of
410 carbonaceous/oxygenated species. This is probably one of the main reasons for the

411 most stable SPI layer, ultimately leading to a better electrochemical performance. It
412 should be considered that alkyl/sodium carbonates are highly soluble at least in
413 carbonate-based electrolytes, while the formed species in the IL-SPI layer, mainly –CN–
414 (286.6 eV) and –S=O– (~532.0 eV) compounds from the Pyr₁₄⁺ cation and FSI[–] anion
415 decomposition reactions are less soluble in ILs. Besides, the F 1s spectra show some NaF
416 formation but to a much lower extent than in the carbonate-SPI layer. NaF can be
417 formed via PVdF dehydrofluorination and/or FSI[–] reduction, as theoretical calculations
418 suggested.⁶⁴ However, considering that the NaF peak is less intense in the IL-SPI layer at
419 any charge states, it can be concluded that NaFSI is rather more stable than NaPF₆
420 and/or that PVdF decomposition is lower in IL media.

421

422 Additionally, the N 1s and S 2p photoelectron lines show IL and NaFSI salt decomposition
423 species after 10 cycles (cf. Figure S5). The N 1s photoelectron spectra at selected charge
424 and discharge states display three peaks after 10 cycles. The small peak at 400.4 eV
425 corresponds to the N[–] anion of the NaFSI salt (Figure S6a), while the peak at 402 eV is
426 assigned to the N⁺ cation of Pyr₁₄⁺ (Figure S6b). The third peak at 399 eV is related to the
427 N[–] anion of an undefined product of the FSI[–] decomposition.⁶⁵ Meanwhile, the S 2p
428 spectra (Figure S5) show two types of S atoms, one connected to N (F–S(O₂)–N–S(O₂)–)
429 and the other one to F (F–S(O₂)–N–S(O₂)–), also presented in the N 1s and F 1s spectra,
430 respectively.^{65–67}

431

432 Finally, the photoelectron spectra show that the peaks corresponding to PVdF at 290.9
433 eV (C 1s) and ~688.3 eV (F 1s) are shifted to lower binding energies when the electrode
434 is charged, while in the discharged state, the initial binding energies of the pristine
435 electrode are recovered. This shift in binding energy of some species upon
436 electrochemical cycling has already been reported and described in terms of an electric
437 potential gradient, also known as a dipole layer, between the bulk electrode and SEI/SPI
438 layer.^{68,69} The electronically insulating electrode components, such as PVdF, are shifted
439 as a function of the electrode potential depending on the state of sodiation, relative to
440 better electronically conducting species.^{68,69} This binding energy shift of PVdF should
441 also be observed in the carbonate-based system, but that is not the case, suggesting
442 that the properties of the formed layer differ depend on the electrolytes. By comparing
443 the carbonate-SPI and the IL-SPI layers, it can be concluded that the latter is more
444 electronically insulating, more homogeneous, and thinner, hence magnifying the dipole
445 effect.

446

447 **3.2.3. SPI Layer Morphology in Carbonate- and IL-Based Electrolyte Systems.** The
448 SPI layer morphology was investigated by SEM (see Figure 5) at OCV (Figure 5a,b) and in
449 the charged state after 10 cycles (Figure 5c,d) in carbonate- and IL-based electrolytes.
450 At OCV, both electrodes show a similar surface morphology. The active material and
451 conductive carbon particles are covered by some species that are heterogeneously
452 distributed. This is in agreement with the XPS observations on the C 1s and O 1s spectra,
453 which show that once the cell is assembled, the electrolyte decomposition occurs and
454 the SPI layer formation initiates.

456 Figure 5. SEM images of electrodes (a, b) at OCV and (c, d) charged after 10 cycles in (a, c) carbonate- and
 457 (b, d) IL-based electrolyte, respectively.

458

459 After 10 cycles, it can be seen that the electrode tested in the carbonate-based
 460 electrolyte (Figure 5c) is covered by a layer. However, it also shows uncovered areas and
 461 some clusters with larger amounts of deposited electrolyte decomposition products. On
 462 the contrary, for the IL-based electrode (Figure 5d), a more uniform film covering the
 463 active material and conductive carbon particles is observed.

464

465 In order to go deeper into this morphological investigation, cross-sectional images of the
 466 cycled electrodes were taken (see Figure 6). Once more, it can be seen that the electrode
 467 tested in the carbonate-based electrolyte does not have a thin and uniform overlayer
 468 (Figure 6a) where in some areas, a thicker layer is observed. Meanwhile, the contrary is
 469 seen for the electrode cycled in IL-based electrolyte (Figure 6b) where a thinner a
 470 uniform layer is observed.

471

472

473 Figure 6. Cross-sectional images of cycled electrodes after 10 cycles in (a) carbonate- and (b) IL-based
 474 electrolytes.

475 It is known that the SPI layer, once formed, protects the electrode from undesirable
476 reactions with the electrolyte during the electrochemical cycling and this may be one of
477 the reasons for the excellent performance of NMFT in the ILbased cell.
478

479 4. CONCLUSIONS

480 The solid permeable interphase formed on P2- $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$ positive electrodes
481 was comparatively studied for the first time in carbonate- and IL-based electrolytes. The
482 comparison performed under the same experimental conditions (cycling rates of 0.1C
483 and 1C at room temperature) clearly demonstrated the superiority of the IL-based
484 electrolyte in terms of cycling stability and safety. The higher stability of P2-
485 $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$ in the IL-based electrolyte, resulting in a rather minor 0.03%
486 capacity fade for each cycle, is due to the possible hindrance of Mn dissolution in the
487 electrolyte and the formation of a thin, stable, and homogeneous SPI layer composed of
488 species including $-\text{CN}-$, $-\text{S}=\text{O}-$, $-\text{SN}-$, and $-\text{SF}-$ groups.

489 In contrast, the carbonate-SPI layer is mostly based on NaF, PEO, NaRCO_3 , and Na_2CO_3
490 species. These latter two species are highly soluble in the carbonate-based electrolyte,
491 leading to the continuous formation and dissolution upon the discharge and charge
492 processes, respectively. The excellent cycling stability of P2- $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$ due to
493 the formation of a stable SPI layer in the IL-based electrolyte opens the way for
494 extending the long life cycle of Na-ion batteries.
495

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501

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